

Non-stationary anisotropy-dependent critical state for clays

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Abstract

In this paper, the effect of fabric anisotropy on the critical state behaviour of clays is investigated. An original concept of moving critical state is elaborated by a novel state parameter-based rotational hardening rule that is subsequently used to formulate a complete anisotropic elastoplastic constitutive model for clays. It is shown that some of the distinctive pre-failure and critical state responses of clays can be explained by adopting a non-stationary critical state line. Furthermore, an enhanced definition for the state of the soil is proposed that provides a more realistic correspondence between the shearing behaviour of an overconsolidated clay to its initial consolidation state. The proposed model is validated by simulating the experimental data from triaxial tests on a number of clays.

Author Keywords: Clays, Anisotropy, Non-stationary critical state

Introduction

The critical state (CS) is defined as a state in which the soil experiences unrestrained shear deformations under constant volume while the stress state remains unchanged. Set on experimental observations (Roscoe et al., 1958; Schofield and Wroth, 1968) and numerical discrete element method (DEM) simulations (Li and Li, 2009), the CS is associated with a

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constant effective stress ratio, commonly known as M , and an ultimate void ratio. These two conditions have been considered necessary and sufficient in the classical CS theory. Based on previously conducted DEM simulations on granular geomaterials, Li and Dafalias (2012) stated that these conditions are necessary but not sufficient for reaching the CS in coarse-grained soils. They proposed the concept of anisotropic critical state theory (ACST) and introduced an additional parameter to implement the role of fabric into the CS and defined a new line in the $e - \ln p$ plane, namely dilatancy state line (DSL), and reformulated their earlier model based on the relative position of this line in the $e - \ln p$ plane. Later on, Theocharis et al. (2017, 2019) proved the incompleteness of the conditions associated with the classical CS concept using DEM simulations and confirmed that the ACST can be used to address the role of fabric at CS.

In the case of clays, several experimental studies have proved that, based on the stress path that the sample experiences, the fabric configuration can be altered from the early stages of the loading up to the CS (Kuganenthira et al., 1996, Hattab and Fleureau, 2010), and its variation affects the clay responses. Recently developed anisotropic models for clays have been mainly developed to deal with their pre-failure anisotropy-dependent behaviour; they ignore the role of fabric anisotropy on the CS response, or safe to say, they do not point out its role explicitly (e.g., Panteghini and Lagioia, 2018; Fuentes et al., 2021).

In this study, supported by experimental evidence in the literature, the role of fabric on the CS is investigated from the numerical outlook by presenting a new anisotropic constitutive model, named AA3-NCSL, with a novel and practical rotational hardening (RH) rule. Furthermore, the concept of the non-stationary critical state line (NCSL) is proposed which provides a new perspective in the definition of the RH rule. This concept relates the rotation of yield surface

to the well-known state parameter and the position of imaginary/instantaneous CSLs in the $e - \ln p$ plane that are defined for the first time in this study.

In contrast to the existing models that mostly try to calibrate the RH rule parameters using a trial-and-error procedure (e.g., Dafalias and Taiebat, 2014) without referring to its consequences in the $e - \ln p$ plane, the proposed model highlights the aspects that should be considered when a RH rule is employed. Regarding this, the new concept substitutes the less practical and hard-to-determine anisotropy variable at CS (i.e., α_{CSL}), which is a common term in existing anisotropic models (e.g., refer to α_c parameter in Dafalias and Taiebat, 2014), with a tangible measure represented by the position of the final CSL in the $e - \ln p$ plot which can be evaluated with relevant test data. The proposed method in defining a meaningful relationship between the fabric anisotropy and the position of the CSL can be adopted by other anisotropic models to determine the ESA as an intuitive task. In other words, the proposed NCSL concept finds a reliable way to calibrate the fabric anisotropy at the CSL by relating it to the position of the final CSL which is a sensible measure with physical meaning. As such, the new concept provides a viable answer to “*There is no known way to calibrate α_c/M by direct measurements*” in Dafalias and Taiebat (2014). In addition, the formulation proposed in the present paper delivers a coherent interpretation of the unique CSL which implies that the uniqueness should be studied for a specific loading direction, and different CSLs might exist for various loading directions (explained in the sequel). Finally, on account of the NCSL concept, an enhanced definition of different overconsolidation states of the soil is proposed.

Definition of State Lines

The isotropic compression line (ICL) is represented by a straight line in the semi-logarithmic $e - \ln p$ plane and as commonly known it can be obtained from isotropic consolidation tests. This line is mathematically defined using the logarithmic expression as

$$e_{ICL} = e_N - \lambda \ln p \quad (1)$$

where, according to Fig. 1b, λ is the slope of the ICL in the $e - \ln p$ plane. e_N is the void ratio of the isotropically normally consolidated clay at $p = 1$ kPa, and it is called the characteristic void ratio of ICL. In this study, the ICL is considered as the reference line and is reserved for the loci of material states related to the normally consolidated soils with ideal isotropic fabric and under isotropic confining stress. Once the fabric anisotropy comes into play or when the applied stress ratio is non-zero (i.e., $\eta = q/p \neq 0$ in which q is deviatoric stress), the ICL is replaced with a new parallel state line that is called anisotropic compression line (ACL) which is characterised by the void ratio e_α , and similar to the ICL, it can be expressed with a simple logarithmic function (i.e., $e_{ACL} = e_\alpha - \lambda \ln p$).

The ACL represents the current stress (i.e., p and q) and anisotropy states of the soil and it moves simultaneously with any variations of material states during plastic shearing (e.g., variation of stress ratio and fabric anisotropy in the case of drained or undrained triaxial test conditions). Analogous to the ICL and ACL, as a novel notion, the instantaneous CSL (ICSL) can also be defined (i.e., $e_{ICSL} = e_\gamma - \lambda \ln p$ in which e_γ is the characteristic void ratio of the ICSL) where can be considered as an imaginary CSL and, similar to the DSL in the ACST (Li and Dafalias, 2012), its location in the $e - \ln p$ plane is governed by fabric anisotropy. As will be elaborated in the following sections, the main difference between ACL and ICSL is the stress ratio that they represent (i.e., ACL is related to the current η while ICSL represents $\eta = M$ which is the slope of the CSL in stress space). It is noteworthy, in general, that the ICSL does not demonstrate the CS conditions, but the final unique CSL can only be considered as a special case of ICSL where the stress and material states represent the conditions associated with the CS. In other words, during the shearing of the sample up to the CS, the ICSL moves

by each variation of the fabric anisotropy and reaches the final position of the CSL that can be expressed by its characteristic void ratio (e_f) as $e_{CSL} = e_f - \lambda \ln p$.

The relative vertical distance between the stress state and CSL specifies the state parameter (ψ) which was first defined by Been and Jefferies (1985). This parameter distinguishes between the lightly overconsolidated (LOC) (i.e., stress state lies above the CSL, $\psi > 0$) and the heavily overconsolidated (HOC) (i.e., stress state lies below the CSL, $\psi < 0$) clays. However, in the proposed concept, the ICSL is replaced with the final CSL. It means that the state parameter is converted to the vertical distance between the stress state and the ICSL. Therefore, the state parameter can be formulated as $\psi = e - e_\gamma$ (i.e., for the normally consolidated clay where the stress state locates on the yield surface and a corresponding ACL, the state parameter can be formulated as $\psi = e_\alpha - e_f$). Moreover, in the case of isotropic clay that is represented by the ICL, the state parameter is referred to as the reference state parameter (ψ_R), where $\psi_R = e_N - e_\gamma$. Based on the definitions established in the proposed NCSL concept, since the ICSL moves with the fabric anisotropy, the reference state parameter is not constant and varies during the plastic shearing.

As will be elaborated in the sequel, from the constitutive modelling point of view the relative position of ICL, ACL, and ICSL with regard to the final CSL is governed by the configuration of the employed yield surface (i.e., shape and orientation). In other words, adopting a flexible yield surface besides a robust RH rule to control the anisotropy enhances the model to capture the pre- and post-failure responses of the soil more accurately.

Model Formulation

In the following, the proposed formulation is presented in the triaxial space and a generalization to the multiaxial space is presented in Appendix.

Bounding surface

To take the advantage of using a robust bounding surface (BS) (Dafalias, 1986), the flexible BS model of Khalili et al. (2005, 2008) is extended in this work into a generalised anisotropic model. In the triaxial stress space, the extended anisotropic BS can be read as

$$f = \left(\frac{\eta - \alpha}{N - \alpha} \right)^{n_y} \ln r_y + \ln p - \ln p_{0i} - \frac{1 + e_0}{\lambda - \kappa} \varepsilon_v^p = 0 \quad (2)$$

in which $\eta = q/p$, n_y and r_y are the so-called shape parameters and N is the general stress-ratio-type shape factor. In addition, α is the parameter that controls the orientation of the BS and represents the fabric anisotropy, p_{0i} is the initial preconsolidation pressure corresponding to the initial void ratio e_0 , and κ is the slope of the swelling line. Finally, ε_v^p is the accumulated plastic volumetric strain due to the shearing of the clay that plays as the isotropic hardening parameter controlling the current size of the BS (i.e., p_0). In other words, the last two terms refer to the size of the BS and can be easily substituted with $\ln p_0$.

Based on shape and orientation of the BS, the positions of ACL and ICSL in the $e - \ln p$ plane can be determined. To this end, consider an ideal isotropic sample that is subjected to a constant- p loading from p_{0i} up to the stress ratio η , as shown by point B in Fig. 1. During the loading procedure, the BS expands from p_{0i} to p_0 and at the same time, its orientation also changes until it reaches the value of α corresponding to the stress ratio. Simultaneously, in the $e - \ln p$ plane the material state moves vertically from the ICL to the ACL which represents the corresponding reduction in the void ratio ($\Delta e^p = \varepsilon_v^p [1 + e_0]$). While throughout the loading process the stress state sticks to the BS and also p remains constant and equal to p_{0i} , the deviation of the ACL with respect to the ICL can be determined using Eq. (2) as $\ln p$ and $\ln p_{0i}$ cancel each other out. Consequently, the vertical distance of ICL and ACL can be expressed as

$$\Delta e^p = (\lambda - \kappa) \left(\frac{\eta - \alpha}{N - \alpha} \right)^{n_y} \ln r_y \quad (3)$$

Since $\Delta e^p = e_N - e_\alpha$, the ACL can be reformulated as

$$e_{ACL} = e_N - (\lambda - \kappa) \left(\frac{\eta - \alpha}{N - \alpha} \right)^{n_y} \ln r_y - \lambda \ln p \quad (4)$$

Figure 1. Constant $p = p_{0i}$ loading in (a) triaxial stress space, and (b) $e - \ln p$ plane

Regarding the definition of ICSL, one can define its mathematical expression in line with the ACL as follows

$$e_{ICSL} = e_N - (\lambda - \kappa) \left(\frac{M - \alpha}{N - \alpha} \right)^{n_y} \ln r_y - \lambda \ln p \quad (5)$$

where it depicts the state associated with the current state of fabric anisotropy, but with the stress ratio $\eta = M$. Now, assume that loading proceeds to the CS, which means that the stress ratio tends to reach $\eta \rightarrow M$, and the fabric continues to evolve simultaneously with the increment of the stress ratio towards the $\alpha \rightarrow \alpha_{CSL}$ which represents the fabric anisotropy state that is associated with the CS. Similar to Eq. 5, the CSL can be formulated as

$$e_{CSL} = e_N - (\lambda - \kappa) \left(\frac{M - \alpha_{CSL}}{N - \alpha_{CSL}} \right)^{n_y} \ln r_y - \lambda \ln p \quad (6)$$

As can be seen, before reaching the fabric anisotropy state corresponding to the CS (i.e., $\alpha = \alpha_{CSL}$), the position of the ICSL depends on the fabric anisotropy and behaves as a non-stationary line in the $e - \ln p$ plane for constant BS shape parameters. In other words, the ICSL moves during the loading process, concurrently with the evolution of the fabric. It can be presumed that before the fabric reaches its equilibrium state, each increment of shearing, which is associated with plastic strain, changes the fabric configuration, and consequently, the clay exhibits a new specific ICSL. Eventually, when the fabric anisotropy reaches the state corresponding to the CS, the ICSL becomes identical to the final CSL. More details on this will be elaborated in the following sections.

Flow rule

The proposed model in this work uses a non-associated flow rule based on the stress–dilatancy relationship proposed by Yu (2007) that has been modified for anisotropic conditions, and it is expressed as

$$d = \frac{d\varepsilon_v^p}{d\varepsilon_d^p} = \frac{(m_p - 1)(\eta - \alpha)^{n_p} + m_p M(M - \alpha)^{n_p - 1} - (m_p - 1)(M - \alpha)^{n_p} - m_p \eta(\eta - \alpha)^{n_p - 1}}{m_p(\eta - \alpha)^{n_p - 1}} \quad (7)$$

where, $d\varepsilon_v^p$ and $d\varepsilon_d^p$ are plastic volumetric and deviatoric strain increments, respectively, and n_p and m_p are model parameters.

Hardening rules

The conventional isotropic hardening rule is embedded in the BS equation, where the produced accumulated plastic volumetric strain governs the size of the BS. However, in the case of the RH rule, a novel formulation is developed by relating the evolution of anisotropy to the relative position of ACL and CSL. The proposed RH rule is comprised of two main components; (1) the governing plastic strain increment, and (2) the equilibrium state of anisotropy (ESA) that

the BS tries to incline along with when the sample is subjected to a specific stress ratio loading.

For that, the RH rule can be expressed in a general form as

$$d\alpha = \mu d\varepsilon_g^p \Delta\psi_{ESA} \quad (8)$$

where μ controls the absolute rate that the BS rotates toward the ESA, $d\varepsilon_g^p$ is the governing plastic strain increment, and $\Delta\psi_{ESA}$ controls the increment of fabric anisotropy toward the ESA.

The same governing plastic strain increment proposed by Dejaloud and Rezaia (2021) is adopted in this formulation. However, in the proposed rule here, using a transitional function (A), the governing strain increment varies between the plastic volumetric and deviatoric strain increments based on η/M ; it reads as

$$d\varepsilon_g^p = H(d\varepsilon_v^p, d\varepsilon_a^p) \quad (9)$$

where $H(x, y) = Ax + (1 - A)|y|$, and

$$A = \tanh\left(a < 1 - \left|\frac{\eta}{M}\right| >^b\right) \quad (10)$$

in which a and b are model parameters that control the variations of $d\varepsilon_g^p$ with regards to η/M .

In order to establish the ESA, the proposed concept uses a new component called target CSL (TCSL) which can be considered also as an imaginary CSL in the $e - \ln p$ plane that the ICSL tends to coincide with. The transition of this line only depends on the stress ratio, and as will be shown later in this section, it reaches the final CSL when $\eta = M$.

Using this definition, the proposed model considers the orientation of BS to evolve continuously until the ICSL reaches the TCSL. For the particular case of shearing until CS, this means that the rotation continues to progress until the stress state or ACL coincides with both ICSL and TCSL that are located at the position of the final CSL in the $e - \ln p$ plane.

Therefore, the degree of anisotropy can be measured using the distance and relative position of ICSL and TCSL with respect to ICL. Regarding this, the increment of fabric anisotropy toward the ESA is considered as a function of the reference state parameters at different stress states, as

$$\Delta\psi_{ESA} = H(\psi_R^{ICL}, \psi_R^{CSL}) - \psi_R \quad (11)$$

where ψ_R^{ICL} represents the location of the ICSL for an ideal isotropic sample when the stress state lies on the ICL, and it can be determined using Eq. (5) by setting $\alpha = 0$

$$\psi_R^{ICL} = (\lambda - \kappa) \left(\frac{M}{N}\right)^{n_y} \ln r_y \quad (12)$$

On the other hand, ψ_R^{CSL} is a model parameter that characterises the final position of the CSL (i.e., CSL when $\alpha = \alpha_{CSL}$), and it can be specified by shearing the sample up to the CS. In other words, in the $e - \ln p$ plane, ψ_R^{ICL} and ψ_R^{CSL} represent the vertical distance between the ICL and the ICSL when the stress state lies on the ICL and final CSL, respectively. In this concept, $H(\psi_R^{ICL}, \psi_R^{CSL})$ is termed as the target reference state parameter (TRSP) that governs the position of TCSL to vary in a range that is limited by ψ_R^{ICL} and ψ_R^{CSL} . In other words, TRSP determines the vertical distance between ICL and TCSL. Finally, as mentioned earlier, ψ_R is the instantaneous reference state parameter which specifies the distance between the ICSL and ICL.

The proposed RH rule considers the ESA with an easily understandable parameter, i.e., ψ_R^{CSL} . This is a clear step forward in comparison to the RH rules of other anisotropic models in the literature that assume an imaginary value for ESA which are mostly evaluated through a trial-and-error procedure (e.g., an ESA proposed by Dafalias and Taiebat (2013) that is a function of a trial-and-error parameter z in their model).

For a better understanding of the mechanism of the RH rule and the coordination between its components, the transitional function A could be examined. Figure 2 shows the role of function A on the variation of governing plastic strain increment and TRSP for different η/M ratios. Note that both vertical axes are qualitative to exhibit how function A provides the necessary transitions by considering η/M variations from the isotropic state ($\eta/M = 0.0$) to the CS ($\eta/M = 1.0$). As can be seen, for an ideal isotropic sample which is subjected to an isotropic loading condition, the governing plastic strain increment is equal to the plastic volumetric strain increment, and the TRSP is the same as ψ_R^{ICL} . With the progress of the shearing, function A makes the role of $d\varepsilon_d^p$ more prominent, while $d\varepsilon_v^p$ gradually loses its contribution to the governing plastic strain increment. Moreover, the TRSP increase toward the value of ψ_R^{CSL} . Finally, at the CS, the governing plastic strain increment equals the deviatoric component of the plastic strain and the CSL reaches its final position where the TRSP is equal to ψ_R^{CSL} . Figure 2 also shows the influence of parameters a and b on the variation of governing plastic strain and the TRSP. Based on the authors experience, $a = 3.0$ and $b = 1.0$ can lead to suitable results by the transitional function.

Figure 2. Effect of (a) a and (b) b variations on the governing plastic strain changes and the TRSP for different η/M ratios

The initial inclination of the BS due to the isotropic or anisotropic consolidation can be obtained by equating the TRSP with the applied stress ratio, η_0 , with the corresponding reference state parameter as

$$H(\psi_R^{ICL}, \psi_R^{CSL}) = (\lambda - \kappa) \left(\frac{M - \alpha_0}{N - \alpha_0} \right)^{n_y} \ln r_y \quad (13)$$

Regarding the adopted RH rule, the anisotropy is stopped from evolving when $\Delta\psi_{ESA} = 0$ (knowing that the governing plastic strain increment is non-zero). This means that anisotropy has reached its equilibrium state (i.e., ESA). Therefore, using Eq. (11), one can determine the explicit form of the equilibrium state (α_e) as follows

$$\alpha_e = \frac{M - \left(\frac{H(\psi_R^{ICL}, \psi_R^{CSL})}{(\lambda - \kappa) \ln r_y} \right)^{n_y} N}{1 - \left(\frac{H(\psi_R^{ICL}, \psi_R^{CSL})}{(\lambda - \kappa) \ln r_y} \right)^{n_y}} \quad (14)$$

Therefore, for any given stress ratio that controls the TRSP (i.e., $H(\psi_R^{ICL}, \psi_R^{CSL})$), the anisotropy variable α varies until it reaches the equilibrium state corresponding to the stress ratio. Knowing that at CSL ($\eta/M = 1$) the target reference state parameter has reached to ψ_R^{CSL} (i.e., $H(\psi_R^{ICL}, \psi_R^{CSL}) = \psi_R^{CSL}$), the equilibrium state at CSL (i.e., the inclination of the BS when the stress state reaches the CS conditions) can be expressed as

$$\alpha_{CSL} = \frac{M - \left(\frac{\psi_R^{CSL}}{(\lambda - \kappa) \ln r_y} \right)^{n_y} N}{1 - \left(\frac{\psi_R^{CSL}}{(\lambda - \kappa) \ln r_y} \right)^{n_y}} \quad (15)$$

Figure 3 shows the variation of α_e for different stress ratios for Otaniemi clay (Wheeler et al., 2003) considering its parameters (i.e., $M = 1.1, \lambda = 0.44, \kappa = 0.04$) and the ones associated with the proposed model (i.e., $N = 1.0, r_y = 1.35, n_y = 1.7$).

Figure 3. The NCSL-based equilibrium state of anisotropy for Otaniemi clay (Wheeler et al., 2003)

The proposed equilibrium state is capable of reproducing the test results with an acceptable accuracy, as can be seen in the Fig. 3. Furthermore, as marked in the figure, the initial state of anisotropy (α_0) for $\eta_{K_0} = 0.67$ ($\eta_{K_0}/M = 0.609$) is almost the same as the one determined experimentally (i.e., $\alpha_0/M = 0.38$ from experiment vs. $\alpha_0/M = 0.37$ determined using the proposed method). It should be noted that the value of $\psi_R^{CSL} = 0.16$ is assumed to get the best fit for α_{CSL} , since there is no test data available to exactly determine this value.

In the case of $\eta/M \geq 1$, as demonstrated by Fig. 3, the proposed RH rule suggests a constant value for the equilibrium state of fabric anisotropy. Therefore, excessive rotation of the BS is inherently prohibited since for $\eta \geq M$, function A in Eq. (10) becomes zero and $H(\psi_R^{ICL}, \psi_R^{CSL}) = \psi_R^{CSL}$. It should be mentioned that according to Eqs. (14) and (15), the proposed RH rule can lead to a constant value of $\alpha_e = M$ if N is considered to be equal to M . This is related to the shape of the BS, but given the flexibility of the adopted BS, this matter does not make any particular numerical difficulty since wide range of surfaces can be readily generated by calibrating the BS shape parameters.

Plastic modulus on the bounding surface

In the case of a complete stress-strain relationship for normally consolidated samples, the consistency condition should be satisfied on the BS to guarantee that the stress state always remains on the BS during the plastic flow. By following a standard differentiation of the BS with regard to stress and its state variables, the plastic modulus (\bar{K}_p) can be obtained as

$$\bar{K}_p = - \left[\frac{\partial f}{\partial \alpha} \left(\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \varepsilon_v^p} d\varepsilon_v^p + \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \varepsilon_d^p} |d\varepsilon_d^p| \right) + \frac{\partial f}{\partial p_0} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \varepsilon_v^p} d\varepsilon_v^p \right] \quad (16)$$

Plastic modulus inside the BS

In the case of overconsolidated samples, where the stress state falls inside the BS, the proposed model uses a radial mapping rule (Anandarajah and Dafalias, 1986) to project the stress state to an image stress point on the BS in order to relate its plastic modulus (K_p) to the one of the corresponding image stress (i.e., \bar{K}_p) via a hardening function (S) as $K_p = \bar{K}_p + S$, in which the proposed hardening function is defined as

$$S = p^3 h_l \cot\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \rho^2 \sqrt{h_l}\right) \quad (17)$$

Where h_l is a shape hardening parameter and ρ is the ratio of the relative distance of the stress state and the projection centre to the relative distance of the image stress point and the projection centre. As discussed by Rezanian and Dejaloud (2021), in BS models, a moving projection centre that projects the stress state of a LOC sample to the sub-critical side of the BS, and the stress state of a HOC sample to the super-critical side of the BS can correctly simulate the stress paths in both conditions. In the proposed model here, the projection centre moves along the α -line and is formulated in triaxial stress space as $p_c = \gamma(p_0 - p)$ and $q_c =$

αp_c where, p_0 is the current size of the BS, and γ is a parameter that controls the position and pace of the projection centre evolution which can be expressed as

$$\gamma = \frac{2p r_y \left(\frac{M-\alpha}{N-\alpha}\right)^{ny}}{p_0 r_y \left(\frac{\eta-\alpha}{N-\alpha}\right)^{ny}} \quad (18)$$

It should be noted that since the projection centre must always lay inside the BS, the value of γ is bounded to a maximum value of $\gamma_{max} = \frac{p_0}{p_0-p}$.

Uniqueness Of the Non-Stationary CSL

Studying the experimental data from tests on different types of clays shows that the CSLs obtained from compression and extension shearings might not be coincident in the $e - \ln p$ plane. Yin and Chang (2009) provided a brief review of experimental tests that were performed on clays of different mineral contents and Atterberg limits. As it was presented, the ratio of the mean effective stress at CSL during extension (p_e) to the mean effective stress at CSL during compression (p_c) varies between 0.74 to 1.5. The projection of these values on the $e - \ln p$ plane confirms that there are two distinct compression and extension CS lines. Furthermore, despite the case of sand material, there is no convincing experimental evidence or DEM simulations to prove the uniqueness of the CSL for clays when they are subjected to the loadings with different directions. Regarding this, it seems that there is a misinterpretation in the literature about the definition of the unique CSL in clays since some researchers have tried to explain that a unique CSL for both compression and extension conditions should be achieved in the $e - \ln p$ plane (Dafalias and Taiebat, 2013, 2014) by considering an identical mean effective stress level at the CSL when a sample is sheared in two different compression and extension directions. However, in a more accurate reading, the uniqueness of the CSL can be scrutinised only when the soil sample is sheared under a specific loading direction and its

position in the $e - \ln p$ plane ought to change continuously with the alteration of the fabric anisotropy. In line with this interpretation, due to the fact that the compression and extension loadings result in different fabric configurations (Kuganenthira et al., 1996), one can consider it as an influential parameter that leads to different CSLs when the sample is sheared in either of the loading directions.

Figure 3 demonstrates the relative positions of the CSL for compression and extension in the $e - \ln p$ plane and their projections in the stress space. As can be seen, after changing the size and the orientation of the BS, each stress path has led to a final CSL based on the level of anisotropy at CS, which is controlled by the value of ψ_R^{CSL} . Regarding this, the CSL related to the extension can be located on the left ($\psi_R^{CSLC} < \psi_R^{CSLE}$) or right side ($\psi_R^{CSLC} > \psi_R^{CSLE}$) of the compression CSL, and they can also be identical ($\psi_R^{CSLC} = \psi_R^{CSLE}$). Therefore, employing a Lode-angle-dependent ψ_R^{CSL} into the model can easily take the variations of fabric anisotropy with regards to the loading direction into account, this leads to a spectrum of CSLs between the ones associated with the compression and extension conditions. Based on the expression proposed by Sheng et al. (2000), the ψ_R^{CSL} can be defined as a function of the Lode angle as follows

$$\psi_R^{CSL} = \psi_R^{CSLC} \left(\frac{2r^4}{1 + r^4 - (1 - r^4) \sin 3\theta} \right)^{1/4} \quad (19)$$

where $r = \psi_R^{CSLE} / \psi_R^{CSLC}$. Moreover, the Lode angle is defined by $\sin 3\theta = 3\sqrt{3}/2(S/J)^3$, where J and S are the second and third stress invariants, respectively. It should be noted that as long as both M and N share the same Lode angle (i.e., $M_c/M_e = N_c/N_e$), ψ_R^{ICL} is independent of the loading direction and is constant.

Figure 4. Schematic illustration of compression and extension undrained triaxial loading in (a) triaxial stress space, and (b) $e - \ln p$ plane

As the CSL position depends on the state of anisotropy, the necessary condition for reaching a unique CSL is to use a robust RH rule that guarantees the BS (or in general, the yield surface) reaches the ESA. In other words, the uniqueness of the CSL is tied closely to the uniqueness of the ESA. Regarding this, by considering the role of anisotropy in shifting the ICSL, it seems crucial to add the term $\alpha = \alpha_{CSL}$ (where α_{CSL} is a unique equilibrium value of the fabric anisotropy at CS) to the conditions associated with CS. This term implicitly implies that the shearing should be continued until the fabric anisotropy reaches its equilibrium state at CS and it should be checked as a confirmation if any model is intended to simulate the CS. However, since the proposed model relates the fabric anisotropy to the position of the final CSL, it satisfies this condition automatically. In a nutshell, the three conditions of $\eta = \eta_{CSL} = M$, $e = e_{CSL}$ and $\alpha = \alpha_{CSL}$ should be checked and satisfied at the CS. Moreover, it should be mentioned that, in line with the ACST concept, the third condition should be satisfied not just for reaching the CS but also for maintaining it. To elaborate more on this statement, consider a clay sample that has reached its CS and the two classical conditions $\eta = M$ and $e = e_{CSL}$ are satisfied. Assume then that at CS one rotates the stress Principal Axes (PA) maintaining fixed stress Principal Values (PV). If the two conditions only were sufficient to maintain CS, the sample should not leave its CS because the stress ratio remains critical (it depends on the on changing

stress PV) and the void ratio is already at its critical state value e_{CSL} for the non-changing during rotation PA. This procedure leads the sample to experience plastic volumetric strain due to the stress PA rotation and necessarily induces plastic loading at the presence of anisotropy by the loss of alignment of the plastic strain rate PA existing during CS shearing; consequently, also the α will start evolving again towards a new CS value. This is why the third condition related to the fabric anisotropy at CS is required in addition to the classical two, for reach and maintaining CS, because upon stress PA rotation this additional third condition is violated and CS is abandoned.

Regarding the above explanations, one can also conclude that if the RH rule is unable to guarantee a unique ESA, it certainly cannot simulate a unique CSL. As an example, one can refer to the RH rule proposed by Dafalias (1986), in which due to using just plastic volumetric strain in its formulation, the rotation of the YS is interrupted as soon as the stress state touches the CSL in the stress space. As a result, this RH rule cannot lead to an identical inclination at the critical state for different loading conditions. In contrast, the proposed RH in this paper continues to rotate the BS until the reference state parameter (ψ_R) reaches the corresponding TRSP which is ψ_R^{CSL} . As the result, a unique critical state can be achieved with this model. However, this point was thoroughly analyzed in Dafalias and Taiebat (2013) and the non uniqueness of the ESA was remedied by a proper and simple change of the RH rule.

Discussion on the NCSL Hypothesis

The NCSL (i.e., non-stationary CSL) hypothesis can help to understand the behaviour of clays under wide ranges of OCR and various consolidation conditions by providing sound justifications based on the experimental observations. Regarding the relative position of the stress state with respect to the CSL in the $e - \ln p$ plane, one can categorise the clay samples based on their undrained responses into four different types of: (I) normally consolidated and

lightly overconsolidated, (II) lightly to moderately overconsolidated, (III) moderately to highly overconsolidated, and (IV) highly overconsolidated samples. In the following subsections, each of the above-mentioned types is examined through evaluation of the conducted undrained triaxial tests on the Lower Cromer till (LCT) samples by Gens (1982) from the NCSL perspective. But first, it is important to review and interpret the test conditions.

Figures 5a and b show the stress paths and stress-strain responses related to a series of undrained compression triaxial tests conducted on the LCT samples which were anisotropically consolidated under maximum axial stress of 350 kPa and $K = 0.5$ and then swelled to different OCR values. Figure 5c also depicts the ICL and CS points which form a band in the $e - \ln p$ plane in addition to the corresponding ACL for the initial consolidation of the LCT samples. The slope of ICL which is represented by λ is equal to 0.067 and its characteristic void ratio is $e_N = 0.799$. Based on the distance between ICL and CS band, ψ_R^{CSL} varies between 0.047 to 0.062, and it is found that $\psi_R^{CSL} = 0.052$ leads to reasonable simulations. The slope of the CSL in the stress space is equal to 1.22 which is the best fit based on the undrained triaxial compression tests. Also, the slope of the swelling line, κ , is 0.009 as reported by Chakraborty et al. (2013). The best-calibrated model parameters for the simulations of LCT behaviour are listed in Table 1 (see Dejaloud and Rezania, 2022 for details of parameter calibration). The initial inclination of the BS due to the anisotropic consolidation under the application of the stress ratio $\eta = 0.75$ is $\alpha_0 \cong 0.1$ which can be determined via Eq. (13). Since the adopted RH rule interrupts the BS rotation when the reference state parameter reaches the TRSP (which is considered a function of the stress ratio), one can conclude that the inclination derived from Eq. (13) is the same as the one obtained from the simulation of constant stress ratio loading.

Figure 5. Experimental data points for the LCT (Gens, 1982); (a) and (b) stress paths and stress-strain responses for undrained compression triaxial tests, and (c) ICL, ACL and CSL in the $e - \ln p$ plane

Type I: Normally consolidated and lightly overconsolidated samples

The CSL corresponding to the initial anisotropy state can be determined using Eq. (6) by considering $\alpha_{CSL} = \alpha_0$. The zone enclosed by the ACL and its corresponding CSL represents Type I. This zone depicts all the samples that their shearing is associated with the tendency to contraction and pore water pressure increment. By the proceeding of loading and evolution of fabric anisotropy, the ICSL moves to the left and the stress state follows it until they meet at the final CSL position that is specified by ψ_R^{CSL} .

Figure 6 demonstrates the model simulation of the normally consolidated LCT sample. Apart from the good capability of the model in simulating the stress path and stress-strain responses (Figures 6a and b), Figure 6c shows how the stress state reaches the final unique CSL the $e - \ln p$ plane. Moreover, Figure 6d reveals what is happening behind the scenes when a Type I sample is sheared up to the CS. In this figure, the vertical axis shows the distance between ACL (blue line) and instantaneous CSL (red line) and the final position of the CSL (Ψ) while the horizontal axis is the normalized stress ratio. As can be seen, both ACL and ICSL move smoothly towards the final position of the CSL during the advancement of the test, and in the end they coincide with each other.

Figure 6. Experimental data points for the LCT (Gens, 1982); (a) and (b) stress path and stress-strain response for undrained compression triaxial test on sample with $OCR = 1$, (c) model response in the $e - \ln p$ plane, and (d) vertical distance of stress state and ICSL with regards to final CSL

As it will be shown later, there is another possibility in the case of Type I samples in which the stress path is followed with a small hoop at its end which indicates a small amount of dilation after a huge contraction. This condition, which is more probable for a Type I sample that is sheared under extension, happens when the initial ICSL is located near to the final CSL. Therefore, by evolution of the anisotropy, the ICSL first crosses the final CSL to the left while the stress state pursues it. Then, both ICSL and the stress state turn to the right and reach the position of final CSL.

Type II: Lightly to moderately overconsolidated samples

In the case of the swelled sample with $OCR = 2$, the fabric configuration does not change during the unloading procedure and the initial ICSL remains untouched. Now, let's consider a sample that its unloading is continued until the stress state locates inside the area between the initial and final CSL in the $e - \ln p$. These overconsolidated samples can be categorised as Type II. Since the sample tends to reach the CSL during the shearing process, the stress state first moves towards the ICSL which is on its right. This part of sample behaviour is associated with the less tendency to contraction (compared to the Type I sample), and in some cases, it might tend to dilation. Meanwhile, by changing the fabric anisotropy, the instantaneous CSL moves toward its destination, and at a specific point, it crosses the stress state to the left. At this point, the stress state changes its direction to follow the instantaneous CSL and a sickle shape is formed in the stress space by the resultant stress path. This transformation comes with the change in the volumetric behaviour in which a tendency to contraction becomes dominant, and the pore water pressure surges. Finally, with the advancement of the shearing, both ACL and instantaneous CSL continue to reach the final CSL position.

Figure 7 illustrates the model simulation for the LCT sample with $OCR = 2.0$. As can be seen, the initial stress state locates between initial and final CSLs (Figure 7c). Thanks to the model

capabilities, owing to the proposed NCSL hypothesis, the sickle shape stress path (also known as hoop type of response) is reproduced with good accuracy (Figures 7a and 7b), unlike what have been presented in literature for simulating the same soil sample with other models (e.g., Dafalias and Taiebat, 2013; Yang et al, 2015). During the early stages of the shearing, as is shown in Figures 7c and 7d, the material state moves towards the moving ICSL and farther away from the final CSL. At point A, where the moving CSL crosses the stress state, the direction of the stress path changes and it continues to track the CSL until both reach their final position specified by ψ_R^{CSL} .

Figure 7. Experimental data points for the LCT (Gens, 1982); (a) and (b) stress path and stress-strain response for undrained compression triaxial test on sample with OCR = 2, (c) model response in the $e - \ln p$ plane, and (d) vertical distance of stress state and ICSL with regards to final CSL

Type III: Moderately to highly overconsolidated samples

Type II and Type III states are almost alike, the main difference between them is related to their relative initial position at the onset of loading with respect to the final CSL, in the sense that at the unloading stage, the Type III sample is allowed to swell until the stress state passes over the final CSL. The main characteristic of this sample is that the stress state cuts across the final CSL to the right to meet the instantaneous CSL and then turns back to accompany it to the end of the shearing. It should be noted that a proper rate of anisotropy provides the opportunity for the stress state to extend to the right of the CSL before reaching the instantaneous CSL. From the volumetric behaviour point of view, Type III samples tend to produce more dilative (or less contractive) behaviour that is followed by a slight contraction. In other words, the tendency to dilation is more profound compared to the contraction in this condition.

Figures 8a and 8b show the model simulation of a Type III sample of LCT with $OCR = 4.0$, in the stress path and stress-strain spaces. A marked observation is that the model readily captures the small U-turn shape at the end of the stress path. This part of the stress path has mostly been overlooked and not been reported in validation of advanced models in the literature, neither in terms of experimental data nor the predictions. In a way, this underpins the legitimacy of the proposed NCSL concept. As is illustrated in Figure 8d, during shearing, the variation of the relative distance between the ACL and the instantaneous CSL with the final CSL follows the same overall trend as in the Type II sample, which includes crossing the final CSL by the stress state and then intersecting the instantaneous CSL before reaching the failure state.

Figure 8. Experimental data points for the LCT (Gens, 1982); (a) and (b) stress path and stress-strain response for undrained compression triaxial test on sample with $OCR = 4$, (c) model response in the $e - \ln p$ plane, and (d) vertical distance of stress state and ICSL with regards to final CSL

It should be noted that the upper bound of the Type III samples in the $e - \ln p$ is the final CSL; however, the lower bound is ambiguous and it can vary based on how fast the fabric anisotropy changes when the sample is subjected to shearing. This is why the lower boundary is shown by a dotted line in Figure 8c.

Type IV: Highly overconsolidated samples

The trait that distinguishes Type IV from Type III is the position where the stress state reaches the instantaneous CSL, which is controlled by the rate of anisotropy evolution and/or the amount that the swelling continues when the stress state passes the ultimate CSL. In other

words, Types III and IV can be interchangeable based on the pace of anisotropy development in the sample. In this soil state, the instantaneous CSL reaches to its ultimate position before the stress state intercept it.

The simulation result of the LCT sample at HOC condition is shown in Figure 9. As can be seen, the proposed model results in very good simulations both in terms of the stress path and the stress-strain behaviour. The point that should be considered here is that the initial stress state is far enough from the final CSL, hence the advancing stress state does not reach it before getting to the CS. As Figure 9d shows, with the evolution of anisotropy, and the ensuing variation of the ICSL's position, both the stress state and the ICSL arrive at the final position of the CSL at the same time.

Figure 9. Experimental data points for the LCT (Gens, 1982); (a) and (b) stress path and stress-strain response for undrained compression triaxial test on sample with OCR = 7, (c)

model response in the $e - \ln p$ plane, and (d) vertical distance of stress state and ICSL with regards to final CSL

Figure 10 shows the newly defined areas in the $e - \ln p$ plane corresponding to different consolidation states of the clay. Given the merits of the NCSL, as demonstrated above, a more distinctive definition for different degrees of soil's overconsolidation state is proposed, which is complementary to the basic conventional definition that considers the CSL as the boundary between two broad LOC and HOC states. This concept also clarifies how anisotropy might affect the boundaries between various overconsolidation states, and lead to switching responses (e.g., from contractive to dilative) that cannot be categorised as definite lightly or highly overconsolidated samples. This subdivision of clay's consolidation state can also be useful for geotechnical modelling purposes as it results in a more accurate prediction of the pre-failure and CS responses with potentially pronounced consequences in boundary value problem simulations.

Figure 10. Boundaries of different sample types

Additional Model Validation

In order to demonstrate the capabilities of the proposed AA3-NCSL model, in this section the model validation is extended to simulate additional available test data on samples of LCT under

different triaxial loading conditions. They include simulations of drained and undrained triaxial tests on both isotropically-consolidated and K -consolidated samples. The model parameters used in these simulations are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters used in the model simulations

Clay	λ	κ	ν	M_c (M_e)	N_c (N_e)	n_y	r_y	n_p	m_p	ψ_R^{CSLC} (ψ_R^{CSLE})	μ	h_l
LCT	0.067	0.009	0.3	1.22 (0.86)	0.8 (0.7)	2.5	1.2	2.5	2.2	0.052 (0.044~0.047)	700	9~10
UC	0.3	0.045	0.3	1.5	1.3~1.4	1.9	1.7	1.1	3	0.232	200	4.5
SC	0.212	0.046	0.2	1.4	1.2	2	1.6	1.1	2.5	0.19	1000	5

Figure 11 shows the simulations related to the undrained triaxial extension tests on the anisotropically consolidated LCT samples together with the triaxial compression tests demonstrated in the previous section. As can be seen, the conformity of simulations with the test data confirms the capability of the proposed model in capturing the extension behaviour of normally consolidated and overconsolidated samples, as well as their compression responses. It is observed that the sample type definitions are valid for the extension cases as well. The sample with OCR = 1 is a Type I sample, where at the latter stages of shearing, it shows a slight dilation while a small hoop is formed at the end of its stress path. Sample with OCR = 2 is still a Type I sample in which the shearing starts with contractive behaviour and then it is completed with dilation. Finally, both OCR = 4 and OCR = 7 samples are categorised as Type IV, which means both samples reach the CS at the same time that ICSL coincides with its final position.

Figure 11. Comparison of data and simulations for undrained compression and extension triaxial tests on anisotropically consolidated samples of LCT (data from Gens, 1982); (a) stress path, and (b) stress-strain responses

Both pre-shearing consolidation and the followed triaxial shearing of K -consolidated tests on LCT samples with various stress ratios (i.e., $K = 1.0, 0.8, 0.667$, and 0.5) are simulated in Figures 12 and 13 to show the capabilities of the AA3-NCSL model in dealing with different loading conditions. As these figures show, the predicted axial strain – volumetric strain response of the model is in good agreement with the test data. In addition, the proposed model shows reasonable performance in simulating the behaviour of Type I samples that are consolidated in different stress ratios. It should be mentioned that the initial inclination of the BS for different tests is determined automatically based on the constant K applied stress ratio in the pre-shearing stage which is the same as can be determined using Eq. (13).

Figure 12. Comparison of data and simulations for the constant stress ratio tests on the LCT (data from Gens, 1982);

Figure 13. Comparison of data and simulations for undrained compression triaxial tests on anisotropically consolidated samples of LCT (data from Gens, 1982); (a) stress path, and (b) stress-strain responses

Furthermore, Figure 14 compares the model simulations and test data for the case of isotropically consolidated samples in four different OCRs. It should be noted that the experimental data over natural clays often show a divergence between the yield stress points for an isotropically consolidated sample with the one subjected to the anisotropic consolidation (e.g., one can refer to the yield stress points of isotropically and anisotropically consolidated Bothkennar clay samples reported by McGinty (2006)). Nevertheless, advanced model simulations in the literature confirm different shape of YS can be adopted to anisotropic and isotropic consolidated samples to best capture the stress path and excess pore water pressure. For example, Sivasithamparam and Castro (2016) argued that the value of the YS shape parameter may not be constant but may depend on the degree of anisotropy; therefore, the BS for the isotropic condition tends to be bullet-shaped, while for anisotropic condition, an inclined ellipse or teardrop-shaped surface best represents the experimental observations (discussed in more details by Dejaloud and Rezania, 2021). Given the above, the simulation of the normally consolidated isotropic LCT samples (undrained triaxial compression and extension) are also carried out using a bullet-shaped BS (i.e., $n_y = 1.2$ and $r_y = 1.7$), and as a result, the associated stress paths are captured more accurately. By comparing simulations obtained from different

BS shape parameters, one can conclude that the proposed NCSL concept leads to a unique CSL regardless of the shape of the BS. Moreover, as can be seen in Figures 13b and 14b, the stress-strain response of the sample is less sensitive to the shape of the BS. The proposed model can also predict the behaviour of lightly overconsolidated samples with decent accuracy. However, the model simulation deviates slightly from the test result for the sample with $OCR = 4$, which by better definition of the shape hardening function (i.e., S) or relating the shape hardening parameter to the OCR, as in Rezania and Dejaloud (2021), the accuracy of the model can be improved. Regarding samples category, one can classify the samples with $OCR = 1$ and $OCR = 1.5$ as Type I, where the shearings are accompanied by pure contraction. This is while the sample with $OCR = 2$ is Type II where the shearing starts with a slight dilation which is then followed by a notable contractive path. This type of behaviour is obvious in both compression and extension. Since the sample with $OCR = 4$ shows a pure dilative behaviour, it can be labelled as a Type IV sample.

Figure 14. Comparison of data and simulations for undrained compression and extension triaxial tests on isotropically consolidated samples of LCT (data from Gens, 1982); (a) stress path, and (b) stress-strain responses

Finally, the drained triaxial behaviour of isotropically and anisotropically consolidated samples are simulated in Figures 15 and 16. As illustrated in these figures, the model is capable of

simulating the drained responses and corresponding volume changes with good accuracy for a wide range of OCRs.

Figure 15. Comparison of data and simulations for drained compression triaxial tests on isotropically consolidated samples of LCT (data from Gens, 1982); (a) stress-strain, and (b) axial strain-volumetric strain responses

Figure 16. Comparison of data and simulations for drained compression triaxial tests on anisotropically consolidated samples of LCT (data from Gens, 1982); (a) stress-strain, and (b) axial strain-volumetric strain responses

Urayasu clay

The isotropic undrained triaxial tests on the undisturbed samples of Urayasu clay (UC), an alluvial clay found along the coastal plains of Japan, are simulated in this section. A full description of this clay can be found in Yamada et al. (2022). Similar to the SC, the value of

the parameter ψ_R^{CSL} is calculated based on the initial and CS stress states of the normally consolidated sample.

Figures 17a and 17b demonstrate the model predictions of the stress paths and corresponding stress-strain curves. Along with them, Figure 17c shows the initial material states (denoted by star symbols), the ICSL corresponding to the isotropically consolidated samples, and the final CSL which is located using determined ψ_R^{CSL} . Besides the good agreement between model simulations and test data, the relative position of the initial stress states with regards to the ICSL justifies different behaviour patterns. For instance, the sample with confining pressure of 98 kPa is located between the ICSL and the final CSL (Type II) and its switching behaviour can be explained on this basis. Moreover, the sample with confining pressure of 49 kPa, behaves as a Type III sample, since the stress state tries to chase the ICSL and skips the final CSL at first, and then it changes its direction when it is crossed by the ICSL.

Figure 17. Comparison of data and simulations for undrained triaxial tests on isotropically consolidated samples of SC (data from Yamada et al., 2022); responses in (a) triaxial stress, (b) stress-strain, and (c) $e - \ln p$ planes

Shanghai clay

Huang et al. (2011) carried out undrained triaxial tests on the isotropically and anisotropically ($K = 0.6$) consolidated natural undisturbed samples of Shanghai clay (SC) that were obtained from the depth of 10 m. Based on the result of conducted oedometer tests, the yield stress was determined to be 110.5 kPa (i.e., the preconsolidation pressure was almost equal to 81 kPa). Based on the conducted isotropic undrained triaxial test with the preconsolidation pressure of 200 kPa and assuming that with this pressure the stress state reaches the ICL, the model parameter ψ_R^{CSL} can be determined using the initial mean effective stress (p_0) and the mean effective stress at the CS (p_c) as follows

$$\psi_R^{CSL} = \lambda \ln\left(\frac{p_0}{p_c}\right) \quad (20)$$

which results in $\psi_R^{CSL} = 0.19$. In the case of SC, the first step of the simulation starts with adjusting the BS shape to capture the reported yield stress points. To this end, Figure 12 shows the calibrated BS with the yield stress points obtained from drained and undrained triaxial tests. The shape parameter values and the orientation obtained are used for model simulations.

Figure 18. Yield stress points of the Shanghai clay (data from Huang et al., 2011)

Figures 13 and 14 show the stress paths and stress-strain responses of isotropic and anisotropic triaxial tests. The good agreement between test data and model simulations by calibrating shape parameters from the yield stress points substantiates the consistency between different components of the proposed model.

Figure 19. Comparison of data and simulations for undrained triaxial tests on isotropically consolidated samples of SC (data from Huang et al., 2011); (a) stress path, and (b) stress-strain responses

Figure 20. Comparison of data and simulations for undrained triaxial tests on anisotropically consolidated samples of SC (data from Huang et al., 2011); (a) stress path, and (b) stress-strain responses

Based on the observed behaviour and model simulations, and by considering the preconsolidation pressure, one can conclude that all the tested samples can be categorized as Type I which includes normally consolidated and lightly overconsolidated samples.

Conclusion

In this study, an innovative concept of the non-stationary critical state for clays was elaborated with an anisotropic constitutive model that adopts a state parameter-based RH law. As a general concept that can be applied to all anisotropic constitutive models for clays, NCSL demonstrates how fabric orientation can affect pre-failure and CS responses. Given for a clay under shear loading the stress state tries to approach the CS from the early stages of shearing, this non-stationary concept can provide superior simulations of stress paths, as the targeted/instantaneous CSL is depending on fabric and loading directions. It should be noted that for a specific loading condition, this proposed critical state still maintains its uniqueness by moving towards its final position when the yield surface proceeds to reach the equilibrium state of anisotropy. In fact, the non-stationary CSL concept provides certain conditions that should be met in any RH rule to satisfy the uniqueness of the CSL. As a consequence of the NCSL, a more realistic definition for the different ranges of overconsolidation for soil has also been proposed, which was established by analysing how the fabric anisotropy caused by the initial consolidation state can affect the shearing behaviour of soils at different overconsolidated states.

Notations

a	Rotational hardening rule parameter
b	Rotational hardening rule parameter
$d\alpha$	Variation of the fabric anisotropy
$d\varepsilon_d^p$	Increment of plastic deviatoric strain
$d\varepsilon_g^p$	Increment of plastic governing strain
$d\varepsilon_v^p$	Increment of plastic volumetric strain
e_0	Initial void ratio
e_{ICL}	Void ratio on the ICL
e_{ACL}	Void ratio on the ACL
e_{ICSL}	Void ratio on the ICSL
e_{CSL}	Void ratio on the final CSL
e_N	Characteristic void ratio of the ICL
e_α	Characteristic void ratio of the ACL
e_γ	Characteristic void ratio of the ICSL
e_Γ	Characteristic void ratio of the final CSL
h_l	Bounding surface parameter
\bar{K}_p	Plastic modulus of the bounding surface
M	Slope of the CSL in the stress space
m_p	Flow rule parameter
N	Bounding surface shape parameter
n_p	Flow rule parameter
n_y	Bounding surface shape parameter
p	Mean effective stress
p_0	Precosolidation pressure
p_{0i}	Initial preconsolidation pressure corresponding to the initial stress ratio

p_c	Mean effective stress of projection centre
q	Deviatoric stress
q_c	Deviatoric stress of projection centre
r_y	Bounding surface shape parameter
S	Shape hardening function
α	Fabric anisotropy variable
α_0	Initial fabric anisotropy
α_{CSL}	Fabric anisotropy at CSL
ε_v^p	Accumulated volumetric plastic strain
η	Stress ratio
λ	Slope of the ICL/ACL/ICSL/CSL in the $e - \ln p$ plane
κ	Slope of the swelling line in the $e - \ln p$ plane
μ	Rotational hardening rule parameter
ψ	State parameter
ψ_R	Reference state parameter
ψ_R^{ICL}	Reference state parameter when $\alpha = 0$
ψ_R^{CSL}	Reference state parameter when $\alpha = \alpha_{CSL}$
γ	Bounding surface parameter

Appendix

This section is devoted to the formulation of the proposed model in the general stress space, where σ_{ij} , σ_{ij}^d and α_{ij}^d represent stress, deviatoric stress and fabric tensors, respectively.

Moreover, infinitesimal elastic strain increment is considered, and the total strain rate ($d\varepsilon_{ij}$) can be decomposed into elastic ($d\varepsilon_{ij}^e$) and plastic ($d\varepsilon_{ij}^p$) components using an additive rule.

Regarding this, the flexible adopted BS can be reformulated as

$$f = \left(\frac{\frac{3}{2} s_{ij} s_{ij}}{p^2 (N_\theta - \alpha)^2} \right)^{n_y/2} \ln r_y + \ln p - \ln p_{0i} - \frac{1 + e_0}{\lambda - \kappa} \varepsilon_v^p = 0 \quad (1A)$$

in which, $s_{ij} = \sigma_{ij}^d - \alpha_{ij}^d p$, $p = \frac{1}{3} \sigma_{kk}$, and N_θ is a Lode-angle-dependent shape parameter.

Moreover, $\varepsilon_v^p = \varepsilon_{ii}^p$ that represents the plastic volumetric strain and $\alpha = \sqrt{(3/2) \alpha_{ij}^d \alpha_{ij}^d}$ controls

the BS orientation. The flow rule can also be expressed with the same formulation as in the

triaxial stress space, by considering $\eta = \|\eta_{ij}\|$ where $\eta_{ij} = \frac{\sigma_{ij}^d}{p}$ and $\|\ \ \|$ represents the size of

the tensor.

The rotational hardening rule can be defined as follows

$$d\alpha_{ij} = \mu d\varepsilon_g^p \Delta\psi_{ESA} H_{ij} \quad (2A)$$

where $H_{ij} = \frac{\eta_{ij}}{\|\eta_{ij}\|}$ is the normalised stress ratio. It should be noted that other components are

defined in the same way as mentioned in the triaxial formulation. Finally, the plastic modulus

in the general stress space is given by

$$\bar{K}_p = - \left[\frac{\partial f}{\partial \alpha_{ij}} \left(\frac{\partial \alpha_{ij}}{\partial \varepsilon_v^p} d\varepsilon_v^p + \frac{\partial \alpha_{ij}}{\partial \varepsilon_d^p} |d\varepsilon_d^p| \right) + \frac{\partial f}{\partial p_0} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \varepsilon_v^p} d\varepsilon_v^p \right] \quad (3A)$$

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